

Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain

D5.1 TraceMyFish Architecture

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ACRONYMS LIST

API	Application Programming Interface
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
IoT	Internet-of-Things
CSV	Comma-separated Values (document)
REST	Representational State Transfer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present report provides an overview of the TraceMyFish Data Platform and the respective architectural and technical choices for implementing it. The drivers for defining the platform were the general requirements for the envisioned iFMS, the sensing solutions defined in the context of WP3, and the data specifications as elicited from the relevant work on WP2 of the project, *Tracking hazards & potential measures*.

Within the report, the architecture for the TraceMyFish data platform and its main components is presented and described, while the technologies and frameworks comprising the TraceMyFish software stack are specified. As the experimental testing and piloting over the platform and the data it generates evolves, more specific methodological solutions will emerge and will be incorporated in the platform. Accordingly, iterative updates on the documentation accompanying the platform's software will be applied and made available via the repositories hosting the platform's codebase.

1 INTRODUCTION

TraceMyFish aims to advance supply system in three geographically distributed blue bioeconomy value chains, by designing and implementing an iFish Management System (iFMS) that will allow the tracking and tracing of safety and quality-critical information across the links of the targeted value chains. Moreover, the TraceMyFish iFMS will establish a secure, trust-enabled data infrastructure, which will collect, pre-process and analyse data coming from innovative, portable sensing devices of different nature and modality (spectral imaging, variegating IoT sensors) and informing specialized AI models and architecture that will enable timely risk prediction to different value chain actors. The examined fish products will carry smart barcodes that, in communication with the iFMS, will carry safety information related to each product and will allow stakeholders and consumers to easily and reliably access this information at any time.

Towards this objective, data management and analysis are crucial for the accurate, timely and secure production and presentation of insights to the users at different stages of the value chain, via easy-to-use interfaces. In this context, WP5 aims to put in place the infrastructure that will realise the data storage and analytics functions required by the platform, develop, train and deploy the AI components that will power the recommendation and decision support features, and build the user-facing applications that will provide access to the data collected throughout the targeted value chains along with the recommendations to the human monitoring a given value chain link.

D5.1 deals with the design of the data infrastructure that will fulfil the aforementioned data requirements. The data platform is built using established and well-supported blockchain frameworks, over which the data ingestion, organisation, indexing and searching functionalities required by the project are applied. The deliverable also entails the implementation of the API mechanisms that will allow the usage of the platform through data providing agents (devices or applications) and client apps.

The present report summarizes the architectural and technical choices for implementing and deploying the platform.

2 DATA PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE

2.1 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN

The overall architecture of the TraceMyFish data platform is depicted in Figure 1 and analysed below.

Figure 1: TraceMyFish architectural design

The TraceMyFish platform will be able to ingest data from different streams, including directly communicating sensors, mobile applications, web applications and cloud-based systems. Data Ingestion is carried out by the respective calls to the TraceMyFish API, accessed via the AAI mechanisms of the iFMS, integrated with the respective AAI mechanisms of the client application (e.g., the VideoMeter Lab software). The data are sent in a tabular object format (either OpenXML supported by MS Excel or CSV) to the Quantum platform to undergo further analysis by the Quantum Pipelines for Pre-processing and Analysis. Communication between the pipeline components is implemented through the use of an Apache Kafka¹ infrastructure for message passing via a message bus monitored by all components.

Analytical results and responses to custom user queries are again carried out via calls to the TraceMyFish API, this time for data consumption but always under the AAI infrastructure of the platform.

The components included in the pipeline are described in the following subsection.

2.2 CORE PLATFORM COMPONENTS

2.2.1 Pre-processing pipeline

The pre-processing modules of the platform will be responsible for the preparation of the incoming data streams before further analysis is possible. On the one hand, the components deal with the identification and annotation/elimination of outlier measurements and identification of gaps in measurement timeseries. On the other hand, harmonization components are responsible for transforming the input data in the representation

¹ <https://kafka.apache.org>

that will be used for ingesting them in the appropriate persistent storage mechanism from the ones described in the relevant section.

2.2.2 AI Pipeline

The AI Pipeline encapsulates all modules responsible for the analysis of the incoming data towards producing predictions and recommendations for assessing food condition and applying mitigative actions in case a hazard is identified. The modules are organised under a workflow that facilitates their re-training in timely intervals as more data and analyses become available, minimising the effort for training, validating and re-deploying the trained models.

2.2.3 Persistence Layer

The TraceMyFish persistence layer incorporates three different storage technologies, to serve different data functions and requirements for the operation of the platform.

A Relational Database solution (MySQL²) is used for storing platform-specific data for operations like user management, device registration and status monitoring, etc. A NoSQL Database (MongoDB³) is used for storing the raw measurement timeseries as delivered by the sensing devices and the applications feeding data in the platform and exported by the pre-processing pipeline. Finally, a ledger infrastructure based on the Hyperledger Fabric platform⁴ is used for installation-bound analytics and processed data, to ensure security and history immutability and preservation.

2.2.4 iFMS API

Data and Analysis Results are exposed via an Authorization-enabled REST API, in order to ensure controlled access to the data by the iFMS user-facing applications and third-party tools in the future. The API will be implemented in PHP, using the Laravel framework⁵.

² <https://www.mysql.com>

³ <https://www.mongodb.com>

⁴ <https://www.hyperledger.org/use/fabric>

⁵ <https://laravel.com>

3 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The report serves as an informative document presenting the communication points and technologies employed towards the implementation of the TraceMyFish iFMS. Consequently, it aims to provide a high-level description of the TraceMyFish technologies, with detailed documentation on the individual components to become available via online public repositories or dedicated documentation websites (especially in the case of the TraceMyFish API). As technical provisions mature, the report will incorporate links to the online resources that will provide further specifications and usage guidelines for the platform, its public APIs and its accompanying applications.